

Key questions, that still remain: how will internationalization be shaped by this global landscape? How will those working in internationalization respond to the challenges they face? And how will they therefore contribute to shaping the future?

Themes for the future are inclusivity and equity, decolonized internationalization, internationalization for society, forced internationalization, internationalization of the curriculum at home, digital internationalization, and the affordability of internationalization.

Decolonizing internationalization reemphasizes the critique of *internationalization as a Western paradigm* (Jones and de Wit, 2014; de Wit, 2020) and the call for '*decolonizing the curriculum*' (Stein, and Andreotti, 2016).

Concerns around the *decolonization and indigenization of curriculum in higher education* are being linked with curriculum internationalization (Buckner & Stein, 2020; Bullen & Flavell, 2021; Leask, 2015; Stein, 2017, 2021; Stein et al., 2020; Stein and Andreotti, 2016).

Implications for Europe and Ukraine broaden its scope;

Taking into account guiding other regional initiatives (ASEAN);

Stronger focus is made on Africa;

EUI lay between stability and growth, between bureaucratic constraints and high ambitions;

We try to solve the negative consequences of Brexit, but mainly in research.

Solidarity as the key component of our future research.

Philip Altbach

GLOBAL TRENDS IN HIGHER EDUCATION: UNDERLYING REALITIES AND CURRENT CRISES

(Філіп Альтбах. Глобальні тенденції у сфері вищої освіти: сучасні реалії та кризи.)

The purpose of this discussion is large – to place global higher education in the context of the significant changes of the early 21st century, to highlight some of the key crisis points of today's complex environment, and to relate these realities to internationalization

My fundamental message is that the trends which have shaped postsecondary education for the past half century remain the main drivers, but with significant new elements that need to inform our thinking – and policy.

First, the main realities.

The development of massification and all that mass enrolments have meant

Increased opportunities for study from a much broader segment of young people – and others . 200 million students worldwide – and India is one of the most rapidly growing HE systems now. More and more young people have the possibility to get a higher education, the result of it according to research is very positive first of all in terms of career, in terms of their happiness. The access to the higher education is not equal to everyone, but it has increased recently.

Mass higher education means diversified higher education system to serve much wider societal purposes, different kind of institutions for different needs. Traditionally in history there was just one kind of universities. They were focused on elite, they were small and they were mostly research focused as well as universities of applied science, community colleges and much else.

The rise of the private sector in higher education is a typical feature in the world system nowadays (and it concerns Ukraine as far as I know) – half global enrolments are in PHE, and most private institutions are of poor quality.

Privatization of public HE in order to pay for the costs of massification.

We know that students have to pay tuition, and in some countries, like for example the USA, it is quite high. And we have a lot of loan systems in order to help students to pay. So we deal with privatization of public HE.

The global knowledge economy which affects all universities all around the world.

Universities have always been international.

Now we are in a period of increasing globalization of science

Scientific globalization crosses borders I have made a research, and we can see that Nobel winners are almost always international scientists. We are in a period of global science. English now is the language of global top level science.

We have seen the rise of global international rankings of universities, these rankings are a part of this global economy.

Mobility of students and faculty is a typical feature of the world HE system and now it means that six million students study all around the world. Internationalization has become a major part of global higher education. Universities have of course always been international.

The European university tradition was international, with the language of instruction in Latin. Now, there are: 6 million global students.. many mobile professors, more than 300 branch campuses many joint and dual degree programs

Internationalization in many way has become an industry and it has become commercialized. \$40 billion to the US economy alone – and similar amounts to other major host countries such as the UK and Australia – at least \$1 trillion globally.

Perhaps most universities that are engaged in internationalization see it as earning resources or even necessary for their survival in terms of student recruitment. There are similar commercial motivations for joint degrees

Internationalization remains a Western-dominated phenomenon, although this is changing. Internationalization seen by some countries as “soft power.”

“Internationalization at Home“ “inclusive internationalization” are positive developments of this process.

Internationalization and mobility were surprisingly little impacted in the long run by the Covid crisis and mobility quickly recovered.

Finally, it is important to point to the key points of crisis in an increasingly unstable and uncertain world—all of these elements directly affect international HE and internationalization—of course in different ways in varied contexts.

Unlike just a few years ago, when the global political environment seemed relatively stable, the situation has significantly changed – and the implications will be significant for the coming period.

The idea of globalization was unquestioned – in the era of populism this has somewhat changed

A huge issue is the possible return of Donald Trump to the US Presidency – this is quite likely This will mean a complete change in US higher education policy concerning internationalization.

Europe may be a bit more stable, but one only needs to look at the election results in Turkey, Hungary, Italy, Slovakia. But at the same time Poland has ended a populist regime.

We do understand, that Ukraine – russia will not be part of European or global HE for a significant period of time. russia may move closer to China but this is not very important and The Middle East is increasingly unstable in the context of the IsraelHamas war.

The importance of immigration policy and practice – not only does this affect national politics in major ways but also has very large implications for higher education internationalization.

Demographic realities have the impact on HE generally and on internationalization

Essentially all of the “global north” countries have declining populations and this will have an impact on HE generally and on international mobility.

Some of the global south continues to rapidly expand HE even though population growth is slowing – Africa and India particularly.

But other regions – Southeast Asia for example – have slower growth or very little expansion.

The impact of Covid was in most respects not as serious as many anticipated International mobility has largely return to pre-pandemic levels.

The impact on students’ mental health has received more attention recently.

And we have the positive aspect of improving the various technologies for distance and hybrid learning and communication.

Clearly we are at the beginning of a new phase of a change that has been occurring for almost a half-century.

Impact on the way science is done in some basic ways as well as on scientific communication has several aspects: impact on the administration and business of universities, the climate crisis sustainability.

So far, universities have done relatively little, but the crisis grows and university responses will deepen.